

Effectiveness of Teaching at the Right Level (TaRL) Approach for Improving Foundational Literacy and Numeracy

Sanjay Budathoki

Programme Manager, Street Child of Nepal(SCoN), Thasikhel-13, Lalitpur, Nepal

Email ID: streetchildofnepal@outlook.comsanjay.budathoki@street-child.org

Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic caused unprecedented disruption to education in Nepal, affecting over nine million children and resulting in severe learning loss equivalent to approximately three years of schooling, according to the World Bank. In response, the Government of Nepal introduced the Recovery and Accelerated Learning (ReAL) Plan to mitigate learning loss and institutionalize accelerated learning practices. Aligned with this plan, Street Child of Nepal (SCoN) implemented the Teaching at the Right Level (TaRL) approach targeting foundational literacy and numeracy skills among Grades 3–5 students.

TaRL employs tailored teaching and learning activities based on students' assessed learning levels, with progress measured periodically. Piloted in 64 schools during 2021–22 alongside partners such as Aasaman Nepal, Pratham Foundation, and the World Bank, the ten-week intervention demonstrated significant improvements. Subsequently, the program scaled to 600 community schools across Madhesh and Karnali provinces, reaching 36,000 children. A 2025 assessment of 12,782 students revealed literacy gains from 31.94% to 85.4% and numeracy improvements from 3.88% to 33.65%.

A comparative 2024 study involving 1,509 baseline and 1,489 endline students across 170 schools further confirmed that TaRL-intervened schools achieved substantially higher proficiency levels. At endline, 57.4% of students in TaRL schools attained the highest literacy proficiency (story level) compared to 31.6% in non-intervention schools; numeracy proficiency (division level) was 30.6% versus 8.8%, respectively.

These findings underscore the effectiveness of the TaRL approach and its potential for broader implementation as a research-backed strategy to accelerate learning recovery. Scaling TaRL can play a pivotal role in ensuring foundational competencies for children, contributing to Nepal's efforts to recover from pandemic-induced educational setbacks.

Keywords: learning loss, Teaching at the Right Level (TaRL), foundational literacy, numeracy, proficiency, accelerated learning